

Supporting Information

Bioresorbable and Wireless Rechargeable Implanted Na-ion Battery for Temporary Medical Devices

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Figure S1. SEM images showing the electrode surfaces before and after evaporation of Mg thin -film. a) Bare NTP-C electrode surface and b) homogeneously deposited Mg thin film onto the NTP-C electrode; c) bare NMO electrode surface and d) homogeneously deposited Mg thin film onto the NMO electrode.

Figure S2. Electrochemical characterization tests using a-c) gravimetric capacity and d-f) volumetric capacity g) Schematic representation of the crystal structure showing the tunnel-type orthorhombic NMO.

Figure S3. SEM images of skin mouse after *in vivo* analyses. a) non-implanted zone, b) battery-implanted zone where black spot remains, c and d) corresponding EDX spectra.

Table S1. EDX elemental analyses of the natural mouse skin.

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
C K	43.09	49.27
N K	19.28	18.91
O K	36.19	31.07
Na K	0.90	0.54
Cl K	0.54	0.21

Totals	100.00
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Table S2. EDX elemental analyses of the remaining black spot after the battery disintegration.

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
C K	43.73	50.00
N K	18.88	18.51
O K	35.61	30.56
Na K	1.03	0.61
P K	0.33	0.15
Cl K	0.43	0.17
Totals	100.00	

Figure S4. Virtual subdivision of Open Field arena.